

DESIGN OF SRAM CELL USING MODIFIED LECTOR AND DUAL THRESHOLD METHOD BASED ON FinFET

Ramesh Gullapally¹, Dr. N. Siva Sankara Reddy² and Dr. P. Chandra Sekhar³

*¹Research Scholar, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, University College of Engineering, Osmania University, Hyderabad.
Email: ramesh.gullapally@gmail.com.*

²Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Vasavi College of Engineering, Hyderabad. Email: nssreddy69@gmail.com.

³Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, University College of Engineering, Osmania University, Hyderabad. Email: sekharpaidimarry@gmail.com.

Abstract

An innovative technology named FinFET (Fin Field Effect Transistor) has been developed to offer better transistor circuit design and to balance the necessity of superior storage system (SS). As gate loses control over the channel, CMOS devices face some major issues like increase in manufacturing cost, less reliability and yield, increase of ON current, short channel effects (SCEs), increase in leakage currents etc. However, the memory must have less power dissipation, short access time and low leakage current. The traditional design of SRAM (Static RAM) using CMOS technology represents severe performance degradation due to its higher power dissipation and leakage current. Thus, a Nano-scaled device named FinFET is introduced for designing SRAM since it has three dimensional (3D) design of the gate. FinFET has been used to improve the overall performance, which includes efficiency, power, and area. Moreover, FinFET has been chosen as a transistor of choice because it is not affected by SCEs. In this work, we have reviewed various FinFET-based SRAM cells and proposed a new 14T SRAM design with Dual Threshold Method and Modified Lector Approach with FinFET which is implemented for the 1bit, 4bit and 8bit and also compared with CMOS technology.

Keywords: FinFET, Dual Threshold, CMOS, Modified Lector, SRAM

INTRODUCTION

For a long time, the integration procedure used by the researchers is the VLSI (Very Large Scale Integration). The process in which millions of transistors are integrated into a single chip, thereby creating an IC (Integrated Circuit) is termed as VLSI. The advancements in the field of VLSI, brings the rise of innovative technologies which further enhance the speed of circuit and also minimize the design constraints. Electronic gadgets have moved to the trend of miniaturization. Today, all the Smart Gadgets (SG) are introduced in small, portable and compact sizes. The most common circuits present in these devices are the memory and processor. For most of the designs, the need for memory is increasing nowadays.

In today's development, beyond 85-90% of the chip area is occupied mainly by memory. The two memory devices, namely SRAM and DRAM provides significant performance for SSD (Solid State Drives). However, there is a necessity for reliable as well as quicker memory for different integrated devices. SRAM [1-2] plays a significant role which offers low-power and high-performance for VLSI applications. Reliability issues give rise to leakage problems, process

variations and SCEs which occur as a result of rapid scaling in CMOS (Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor) [3] design. SRAM is faster, reliable and consumes less power [4] however; it was affected by CMOS scaling [5-6] triggering process variations.

CMOS size shrinking makes the scaling of dimensions possible, which further results in stability and power issues. In CMOS devices, the main problem is the scaling of supply voltage causes threshold voltage scaling. Due to Moore's law, the CMOS scaling is transformed into nano-scale system [7]. Therefore, CMOS scaling has now come to a limit with the following possible alternatives such as FinFETs [8], TFET (Tunnel FET) [9], and CNTs (Carbon Nano Tubes) [10].

Among these alternatives, FinFET technology [11-12] is chosen as the best option for replacing CMOS. FinFET provides several advantages over bulk CMOS, for instance, higher speed, higher drive current for a given transistor footprint, lower leakage, no random dopant fluctuation, lower power consumption, better mobility and transistor scaling.

Several low power techniques named Variable threshold CMOS (VTCMOS), Multi-threshold CMOS (MTCMOS), Self controllable voltage level (SVL), Stacking, Power gating are also used to minimize the leakage current and power dissipation. Initially, SRAM is designed using traditional CMOS. However, this creates some problems like increase in leakage current and high power dissipation which disturbs the SRAM performance. The memories need to have low leakage current, shorter access time and less power dissipation. So, FINFET based SRAM cells are suggested over CMOS based SRAM cells [13]. SCEs are minimized using FinFET design when compared to CMOS based design structures [14]. Also, to improve the cell stability, it is essential to shrink the leakage characteristics of SRAM cells [15].

The downsizing of semiconductor devices has emerged as the best approach to electronic headway to get higher speed, lower cost, lower power dissipating and for the higher handiness of semiconductors. In 1965, Gordon Moore, individual sponsor of Intel had expected that the amount of semiconductors on a chip would twofold at standard spans, which transformed into the prominent Moore's Law. In the past couple of years, semiconductor industry had gone through immense movements by extending the amount of semiconductors on a chip by diminishing the component size. Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistors (MOSFETs) had become the establishment of the present Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) in light of the cutting back of semiconductor sizes clinging to the Moore's Law. Over the latest twenty years, the size of the MOSFET has contracted from incorporate size of a couple of microns to 32 nm. As the part size is contracting reliably, various issues like short channel impacts, channel incited prevention cutting down, limit voltage decline, etc had started to influence the introduction of MOSFET contraptions. As the doorway oxide thickness is decreased, spillage current augmentations at a higher rate inciting higher power use and a languid speed of the contraption. In the more significant nanometer framework, non-ideal credits not exactly equivalent to MOSFETs are taken note. To determine these issues, various new nanotechnology devices like FinFET, Silicon on Insulator (SOI) MOSFETs, Carbon Nanotube Field Effect Transistors (CNTFET), Graphene Nanoribbon Field Effect Transistors (GNRFET, etc, had been investigated over ongoing years[16].

August : Theme 1

Biomechanical Engineering, Digital Manufacturing, Engine and Automotive Engineering, Fluid Mechanics

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8241027

Semiconductor memories are moreover considered as the primary microelectronic pieces of electronic reasoning structure plan, for instance, PCs based application. Semiconductor memory displays are good for taking care of tremendous measures of cutting edge information which are principal for all modernized systems. The proportion of memory required in a particular structure depends upon the sort of use, anyway the amount of semiconductors required for limit work is greater than for reasoning exercises and various applications. The consistently growing interest for tremendous limit has driven the creation development and memory progression towards higher data amassing densities. On-chip memory groups have become comprehensively used subsystems in VLSI circuits and monetarily available single chip read/form memory limit has shown up at 1 GB. The semiconductor memory is generally organized by the kind of data storing and data access. Examine/create memory or Random access Memory (RAM) ought to permit the distinction in data bits set aside in the memory show, similarly as their recuperation interest. The set aside data is temperamental. SRAM is mainly used for hold memory in chip, brought together worker PCs, planning workstations and memory in managed devices due to high speed and low power use. Memory cells are created using semiconductors. The amount of semiconductors used in a single chip may increase certainly for reliably subject to Moore's law. Notwithstanding the way that they give fast of movement, lower spillage and lessened semiconductor count, they become less useful when the area decreases underneath 32nm. Overall advancement Roadmap for semiconductors (ITRS) gives information about late examples and progress in semiconductor development.

The presence of tip top VLSI chips require a cutting edge method to store electronic data, on chip to address execution issues. SRAMs are the pinnacle of such courses of action. SRAMS are an essential piece of a wide extent of microelectronic contraptions. Customer demand advocates a reduction in size of memory storing devices. With advances in scaling growing, new hindrances are introduced on usage of sub 10nm MOSFETs in tremendous extension joined (VLSI) circuit plan, similar to affectability to deal with assortments and development in semiconductor spillage. Scaling has shown up at a fundamental apogee where the spillage streams have become a critical setback. Such results demand another FET development overall. An affable response to such demands was given by the presence of graphene.

In today's era, one of the most suitable forms of FET is FinFET technology [17]. This permits the execution and simulation of transistor applications in a faster way both in analog as well as digital domains. FinFET seems to be a better option for the future nano electronics because of its following characteristics such as compact susceptibility, high performance, minimized manufacturing costs and low power consumption [18–19]. The bulkCMOS transistors can be replaced by means of FinFETs [20]. This technology is an appropriate option for the design of memory sub- systems due to its standby power or low leakage current property [21].

The diagrammatic representation of FinFET is mentioned in Fig. 1[22]. The FinFET structure includes multiple perpendicular channels that appear similar to 'Fin' of fish, so it is named as FinFET. It is also known as multi-gate device (MGD) which is built on a substrate. The gate is positioned on two, three or else four sides of the channel which forms a double gate arrangement. The source or drain region forms 'Fin' on the surface of silicon. The other name of FinFET is

multi-gate transistor.

Figure 1: Structure of FinFET[22]

FinFET transistors can operate on the dual model, namely Tied-gate (TG) and Independent-gate (IG) mode [21]. The 3D representation of FinFET- TG and IG mode is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: (a) TG FinFET 3D-view (b) IG FinFET 3D-view

In TG-mode, both of the front, as well as back gates (FBGs), are tied to a similar control signal (CS). The design of TG- FinFET is simpler with shorted FBG. The SCEs are avoided by the TG-mode because this mode has greater gate-to- channel coupling. IG-FinFET combines the P-type parallel FinFET and ties with the BGs of N-type to ground in order to attain equivalent rising as well as falling delays. Both the FBGs are tied to different control signals in the IG-mode. FinFET devices ensure higher current density and faster switching times than CMOS technology. Also, by minimizing the off-state leakage, the SCEs are controlled.

Various design options are offered by the FinFET structures. It works on various modes such as IG, TG, hybrid and low power mode. The combination of both IG and low power mode is known as hybrid mode [23]. FinFET devices are similar to CMOS device from the view of Fabrication. But, FinFET offers superior performance gains at very low power due to higher gate control. To suppress the SCEs, gate-dielectric leakage currents, the FinFET devices are used. FinFET is a favourable technique to bridge the technology gap between bulk CMOS and other novel devices, such as CNTFETs and Graphene FETs. Thus, FinFET technology is introduced as a new procedure for designing an SRAM cell with ultra-low leakage.

12T SRAM Cell

The proposed 12T piece cell in [24] drastically improves the compose edge by taking out the charge dispute because of the input design of a SRAM cell. Its inborn construction permits solid activity during composing by hindering the force supply course. Since there is no charge dispute, no measuring imperative exists. To improve RSNM, pull-up gadgets can be measured multiple times more than the draw down gadgets for adjusting the VTCs of consecutive inverters. Also, any gadget can be estimated by a specific presentation necessity since there is no measuring limitation in the proposed structure. The VTC of the proposed cell in WSNM is basically the same as the best bends recommended in Section 1 because of the criticism free construction during compose. In three unique meanings of compose edge including WSNM, CWMM, and BLWM, the 12T cell is more hearty than the customary 6T and 8T cells, and it is equivalent to the 10T cell. Furthermore, the proposed 12T cell is more powerfully stable than the 6T, 8T, and 10T cells. In this way, the proposed cell accomplishes a higher WSNM, BLNM, and DNM without forfeiting RSNM. Appropriately, the proposed 12T cell can be utilized for super low force applications which requires low voltage activities while requesting moderately low limit since the space of memory block is tantamount to the space of fringe hardware. Furthermore, the WSNM logical model of the 12T cell is proposed. The super-limit model fits inside 8.7% mistakes, while the subthreshold model fits inside 14.2% blunders. When β proportion changes from 1 to 5, the super-edge model fits inside 6.17%, while the subthreshold model fits inside 15.42% errors[31].

In the paper [25], creators propose two fourfold cross-coupled hook based SRAM bit-cells for profoundly solid earthly applications. Contrasted and the greater part of the thought about SRAM cells, the proposed QUCCE 10T and 12T have practically identical or better delicate blunder resilience, RSNMs, and HSNMs at ostensible inventory voltage. As to the strength, the QUCCE 10T and 12T are about $2\times$ and $3.4\times$ the base basic charge of the customary 6T separately. Notwithstanding, the QUCCE 10T highlights a high compose blunder rate in close to edge voltage area, which implies it can't be utilized in low voltage applications despite the fact that it has high understood dependability. What's more, the QUCCE 10T has equivalent or lower region overhead contrasted and the majority of the considered cutting edge delicate mistake lenient SRAM bit-cells. Thus, the QUCCE 10T is a decent decision for profoundly dependable high-thickness earthly applications at ostensible stockpile voltage. QUCCE 12T displays about 56% region and half spillage power punishments over the customary 6T. In any case, contrasted and a large portion of the referential cells including the 6T, the QUCCE 12T saves over half the read admittance time,

making it appropriate for fast SRAM plans, and it likewise has the best understood edge, with the exception of the 8T, as far as the μ/σ proportion in close to limit voltage district among the wide range of various cells which almost have no compose disappointment around there. Taking the three impediments, referenced before as the expanded postponement, diminished read steadiness and expanded compose blunder rate, of applying close/subthreshold voltage in SRAM plans into account, the proposed QUCCE 12T is a promising contender for future exceptionally solid earthbound low-voltage applications. Besides, like DICE and Quatro, the QUCCE construction can likewise be utilized to plan delicate mistake lenient hooks, goes back and forth or registers.

In the paper [26], Authors present a novel profoundly dependable 12T cell with decoupled peruse and compose ports. Recreation results have shown the ordinary capacities and delicate mistake resistance of the proposed. Contrasted and the wide range of various bitcells, the proposed 12T has the biggest RSNM, and it additionally saves 85.4% read admittance time by and large. Also, it shows 42.2% spillage power punishment over the customary 6T. These outcomes being thought of, the proposed double port 12T is reasonable for rapid exceptionally dependable applications.

Figure 3: 12T SRAM cell

A tale RHPD-12T memory cell with high unwavering quality and speed was proposed brief IN [27-28]. Contrasted and different radiation-solidified memory cells, the proposed RHPD-12T cell can keep from any single-hub upset, yet in addition has better circuit execution at high recurrence and low force supply voltage. Among the entirety of the referential cells, including the DICE cell, RHPD-12T can save over 40% of compose access time, keep up great composing capacity even in close limit voltage district, and it additionally has the best hold and compose edge among the wide range of various cells, which makes it reasonable for fast and high-unwavering quality SRAM plans. Consequently, the proposed RHPD-12T cell displayed in Figure 3 can be viewed as a decent plan for aviation applications, as it's anything but a decent harmony between radiation power and circuit execution. A delicate mistake lenient RHMC-12T SRAM cell is proposed utilizing the circuit level solidifying method. The proposed design is equipped for recuperating both "0" to "1" and "1" to "0" SEU mistake at any delicate hub. Contrasted with the current radiation solidifying memory cells, the proposed engineering is more insusceptible to delicate mistake as the all out

number of touchy hubs are decreased from 4 to 2. The decrease in the absolute touchy region makes the proposed cell best possibility for the SRAM cells to be utilized in the radiation climate.

PROPOSED 14T SRAM CELL

At last, the typical 6T SRAM cell is utilized as center putting away fragment and key piece of PC plans and construction in CMOS improvement. The immediate arrangement of 6T SRAM with colossal breaking point limit makes its appropriate part, yet experiences read/make fight, half-select unsettling effect and read upset [27]. The reliability of standard Si-CMOS SRAM cell at low stock voltage is genuinely inconvenient which corrupts totally with supply voltage scaling and its show influence

Figure 4: 14T SRAM cell with dual Threshold and modified Lector Approach

because of VMIN necessities [27]. At last, the typical 6T SRAM cell is utilized as center putting away fragment and key piece of PC plans and construction in CMOS improvement. The immediate arrangement of 6T SRAM with colossal breaking point limit makes its appropriate part, yet experiences read/make fight, half-select unsettling effect and read upset [27]. The reliability of standard Si-CMOS SRAM cell at low stock voltage is genuinely inconvenient which corrupts totally with supply voltage scaling and its show influence because of VMIN necessities [28]. To work on the fearlessness and execution of low force SRAM plan at low store voltage have been proposed by various analysts [28-30]. The read security can be worked on in various SRAM cell by utilizing read maintains which fundamentally update the read steamed and accomplished read

SNM indistinguishable from hold SNM [29-31]. In the SRAM cell investigate and structure help frameworks with isolating utilized with covered digit line, negative-VSS and word-line-under-drive for boosting read tasks and negative-cycle line, word-line-over-drive and transient-voltage-breakdown for make boosting works out, with refreshing the strength of pull down to pass entryway and surrender entrance to pull, freely [32-34]. Disproportionate SRAM cell works on the read security by increment strength pull-down with single read port which essentially decline read upset [35]. Regardless, the information system is utilized to reduce read upset which gives fundamentally improvement in consistency by restricting the telephone collecting focus from read bitline, still endure read upset. The examination NMOS semiconductors actuate gliding focus point putting away which in addition impacts spillage current in subthreshold area conceivably initiate delicate mess up and various cell upset happens [36]. The different cells upset can be confined by utilizing the piece interleaving plan with fumble check and modification [37]. The standard 6T SRAM cell isn't legitimate for digit interleaving structure due to picked wordline (WL) perform pseudo read development which debases vigor [38-39]. Make half-select unsettling influence can be taken out by applying cross-point make planning onboth line and segment based structure wordline (WL) structure, they truly endure make upset which degenerate writeability. Hence, a novel single finished marvel free FinFET-based 14T SRAM cell working at low stock voltage close to restrict voltage area is proposed in this paper. The proposed cell disposes of the make half-select issue utilizing cross-point access, read cushion utilized for read reliability improvement, single bitline utilized for increment thickness and reducing power use.

A twofold limit voltage method is helpful for power decrease in a functioning methodology for activities and it essentially diminishes the spillage current in the lethargic mode. SNM of the cell with the low voltage limit (LVT) gadgets is higher than the cell with the high voltage edge (HVT) gadgets. Along these lines, the choice apprehensive voltage decision is quick in organizing of a common SRAM cell [40-41]. The cell with low-limit voltage contraptions has solid unsettling influence resistance than the cell with high-edge voltage. This on a very basic level requires the decision of the stock voltage of contraption under 0.5V, 16 nm in low spillage FinFET progression to further develop the force utilization in the proposed SRAM plan. The stock voltage of 325mV is streamlined for the 16 nm low spillage FinFET-based SRAM plan.

Overwhelmingly T10 semiconductor uses to lessen the conveyance way issue in the circuit as it drives with make line. T10 will go ON precisely when make line sets up. So in this examination I need to focus in on two things, one is to utilize T10 which is indisputable for normal 6T and 8T SRAM cells. Second to utilize twofold edge framework. The standard 6T SRAM faces read/make fight which degenerate the presentation and strength. To reduce the read upset, make bitline is separated from the read bitline which requires an other read line (WL) in 8T SRAM cell. The structure line (WL) influences half-select issue during interleaving region partaking considering charge direct from bitline into the internal focus of the 8T SRAM cell. The half-select issue annoyed with an expansion in the measure of memory cells on the bitline. A particular finished method is a valuable procedure for gigantic force spread decreasing in the SRAM memory cell. It additionally essentially diminishes spillage current and chip plan region . The one piece of the

extraordinary dynamic can be diminished by utilizing this single-finished course of action. In any case, it adulterates the acquaintance of SRAM cell with the degree inspected/structure delays at the low stock voltage. To beat these difficulties unmistakable analyze and make help strategies were proposed, for example, examination read/make help, unequal read/structure – help, twofold edge voltage, cross-point-information cautious, and force support. We propose another single-finished FinFET-based 14T SRAM cell in this Research. Fig.2 shows the schematic circuit outline of a normal single-finished clash free FinFET based 14T SRAM cell plan. The proposed cell incorporates two cross-coupled inverters inv1 (T1 and T2) and inv2 (T5 and T4) used to store information on focus Q and Qn. The showcase of the proposed 9T SRAM cell can be improved by utilizing an other read/structure port, (T5-T9). The new 14T SRAM cell has a 2.8× more analyzed miracle hindrance when wandered from 8T SRAM cell at immaterial area overhead considering bound read port, (T7, T8 and T9). The semiconductors assessing degree (T5/T9) of structure port is climbed to 1.8 to further develop as far as possible and strength out of SRAM cell. The piece interleaving approach is planning to lessen coupling complain and work on the delicate mess up. The line section select line is utilized to further develop bunch capacity and decrease region overhead which uses the monstrous number of cell on piece line.

LECTOR APPROACH

Narender Hanchate et al, proposed a novel technique called LECTOR (Refer Fig. 5) for reducing leakage power in CMOS circuits. He introduced two leakage control transistors (LCT) a PMOS and NMOS within the logic gate. The gate terminal of each LCT is controlled by the source of the other. In this arrangement, one of the LCT's is always near its cut off voltage for any input combination. This increases the resistance of the path from Vdd to ground leading to significant decrease in leakage currents. This technique works effectively in both active and idle, states of the circuit, resulting in better leakage reduction. The experimental results indicate an average leakage reduction of 79.4% for MCNC benchmark circuits.

Figure 5: LECTOR technique

SRAM stands Static Random Access Memory. It finds application in CPU Cache, Personal Computers, workstations, routers, hard disk buffers and router buffers. The advantage of SRAM is that it does not require periodic refreshment unlike DRAM. It is also volatile i.e. the data is lost once the power is turned off. The construction of a 6T SRAM cell consists of 2 PMOS and 4 NMOS transistors. The operation of SRAM cell is explained by considering 6T SRAM cell as an example. From the figure 3 we can understand the circuit diagram of 6T SRAM cell.

The operation of SRAM can be divided into three states: read, write and hold state. During write operation, the voltage of WL is increased and Bit lines BL and BL' are raised to Vdd or with necessary values. The new bit line value overpowers the existing value. During read operation, the WL voltage is raised high, the memory cell discharges either BL or BL' depending on the stored data on the nodes Q and Q'. During Hold state, the voltage in WL is held low and the BLs are left floating or driven to Vdd. Each bit in an SRAM is stored on four transistors that form two cross-coupled. This storage cell has two stable states, which are used to denote 0 and 1. Two additional access transistors control the access to storage cell during read and write operation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed design has been simulated in HSpice. The design with dual threshold has been simulated by both using FinFET and CMOS. The table 1 shows the comparison of the SRAM cell with FinFET and CMOS, where the GNRfet shows the very accurate less power when compared with the FinFET. Figures 6 and 7 shows the waveforms for both FinFET and CMOS respectively. Table 4,5,6 shows the total technology Parameters.

Table 1: Comparison with FinFET and CMOS of 14T SRAM Cell 1 bit

S.NO.	NM	Power in mW for CMOS	Power in mW for FinFET
1	22	6.08	3.57
2	14	5.32	3.28
3	10	5.76	2.67
4	7	5.68	2.53

Table 2: Comparison with FinFET and CMOS of 14T SRAM Cell 4 bit

S.NO.	NM	Power in nW for CMOS	Power in nW for FinFET
1	22	2.81	1.35
2	14	2.36	1.26
3	10	1.92	1.22
4	7	1.82	1.19

Table 3: Comparison with FinFET and CMOS of 14T SRAM Cell 8 bit

S.NO.	NM	Power in nW for CMOS	Power in nW for FinFET
1	22	3.01	1.92
2	14	2.62	1.72

3	10	2.21	1.65
4	7	1.98	1.58

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: FinFET Waveforms in Hspice and CMOS Waveforms in Hspice

Table 4: Technology Parameters 22nm-1bit

S.NO.	PARAMETER	VALUE
1	Power_avg	3.5702E-05 from= 0.0000E+00 to= 2.0000E-07
2	Avgpwr	3.5989E-05 from= 5.0000E-09 to= 2.0000E-07
3	q_rise_delay	Failed
4	Trig	not found
5	Tpd	2.7406E-11
6	qn_rise_delay	2.7406E-11
7	qn_fall_delay	-2.9433E-11
8	SupplyCurrent	1.5602E-05 from= 0.0000E+00 to= 1.0000E-08
9	Static power	-7.8011E-06

10	high_low_total_energy	3.8728E-14
11	low_to_high_total_energy	3.9283E-14
12	dynamic_energy	7.8011E-14
13	total_dynamic_energy	3.9005E-14
14	total_dynamic_power	-1.2346E-29

Table 5: Technology Parameters 22nm-4 bit

S.NO.	PARAMETER	VALUE
1	Power_avg	1.3515E-09 from= 0.0000E+00 to= 2.0000E-08
2	Avgpwr	1.3515E-09
3	q_rise_delay	3.6266E-11 targ= 8.0944E-11 trig= 4.4678E-11
4	Trig	4.4678E-11
5	Tpd	2.1673E-11 trig= 2.1673E-11
6	qn_rise_delay	1.8714E-10
7	qn_fall_delay	3.8400E-11
8	SupplyCurrent	6.5328E-10
9	Static power	5.8795E-10
10	high_low_total_energy	5.8867E-18
11	low_to_high_total_energy	7.2297E-21
12	dynamic_energy	5.8795E-18
13	total_dynamic_energy	2.9398E-18
14	total_dynamic_power	1.2346E-29

Table 6: Technology Parameters 22nm-8 bit

S.NO.	PARAMETER	VALUE
1	Power_avg	1.9230E-09 from= 0.0000E+00 to= 3.0000E-08
2	Avgpwr	1.9230E-09
3	q_rise_delay	3.6266E-11 targ= 8.0944E-11 trig= 4.4678E-11
4	Trig	2.1673E-11
5	Tpd	2.1673E-11
6	qn_rise_delay	-1.8714E-10 targ= 2.1673E-11 trig= 2.0881E-10
7	qn_fall_delay	3.8400E-11 targ= 8.2810E-11 trig= 4.4410E-11
8	SupplyCurrent	1.3066E-09
9	Static power	-1.1759E-09
10	high_low_total_energy	1.1773E-17
11	low_to_high_total_energy	-1.4459E-20
12	dynamic_energy	1.1759E-17
13	total_dynamic_energy	5.8795E-18
14	total_dynamic_power	-1.2346E-29

CONCLUSION

By performing this research we have analysed SRAM cell using modified lector and dual threshold method based on FinFET, which has been implemented for 1bit, 4bit and 8bit. Power has been decreased upto 60% when compared to CMOS. Successfully designed and tested the SRAM with dual threshold and modified lector approach.

References

- 1) Agrawal, R., & Tomar, V. K. (2018). Analysis of Low Power Reduction Techniques on Cache (SRAM) Memory. In 2018 9th International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), IEEE, 1–7
- 2) Pasandi, G., Mehrabi, K., Ebrahimi, B., Fakhraei, S. M., Afzali-Kusha, A., & Pedram, M. Low-power data encoding/decoding for energy-efficient static random access memory design. *IET Circuits, Devices & Systems*, 13(8), 1152–1159
- 3) Lin, Z., Wu, X., Li, Z., Guan, L., Peng, C., Liu, C., & Chen, J. (2016). A pipeline replica bitline technique for suppressing timing variation of SRAM sense amplifiers in a 28-nm CMOS process. *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, 52(3), 669–677
- 4) Chiu, P. F., Chang, M. F., Wu, C. W., Chuang, C. H., Sheu, S. S., Chen, Y. S., & Tsai, M. J. (2012). Low store energy, low VDDmin, 8T2R nonvolatile latch and SRAM with vertical-stacked resistive memory (memristor) devices for low power mobile applications. *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, 47(6), 1483–1496
- 5) Mocuta, A., Weckx, P., Demuynck, S., Radisic, D., Oniki, Y., & Ryckaert, J. (2018). Enabling cmos scaling towards 3nm and beyond. In 2018 IEEE Symposium on VLSI Technology IEEE, 147–148
- 6) Yusop, N. S., Nordin, A. N., Khairi, M. A., & Hasbullah, N. F. (2018). The impact of scaling on single event upset in 6T and 12T SRAMs from 130 to 22 nm CMOS technology. *Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids*, 173(11–12), 1090–1104
- 7) Zhang, K. (2018 Nov 5). Circuit design in nano-scale CMOS technologies. In 2018 IEEE Asian Solid-State Circuits Conference (A-SSCC) IEEE, 1–4
- 8) Ensan, S. S., Moaiyeri, M. H., Moghaddam, M., & Hessabi, S. (2019). A low-power single-ended SRAM in FinFET technology. *AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, 99, 361–368
- 9) Liautard, R., Trojman, L., Arevalo, A., & Procel, L. M. (2019). TFET and FinFET Hybrid Technologies for SRAM Cell: Performance Improvement over a Large VDD-Range. 2019 IEEE Fourth Ecuador Technical Chapters Meeting (ETCM) (pp. 1–5). IEEE
- 10) Jia, X., & Wei, F. (2019). Advances in production and applications of carbon nanotubes. *Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes* (pp. 299–333). Cham: Springer
- 11) Birla, S. (2019). FinFET SRAM cell with improved stability and power for low power applications. *Journal of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 14(2), 1–8
- 12) Birla, S. (2019). Variability aware FinFET SRAM cell with improved stability and power for low power applications.
- 13) Panchal, J., & Vishal, R. (2017). Design And Implementation Of 6t Sram Using Finfet With

Low Power Application.2395-0056

- 14) Narendar, V., & Mishra, R. A. (2015). Analytical modeling and simulation of multigate FinFET devices and the impact of high-k dielectrics on short channel effects (SCEs). *Superlattices and Microstructures*, 85, 357–369
- 15) Tripathi, T., Chauhan, D. S., & Singh, S. K. (2018). A Novel Approach to Design SRAM Cells for Low Leakage and Improved Stability. *Journal of Low Power Electronics and Applications*, 8(4), 41
- 16) C. R. Manoj, Meenakshi Nagpal, Dhanya Varghese, and V. Ramgopal Rao, " Device Design and Optimization Considerations for Bulk FinFETs", *IEEE transactions on electron devices*, Vol. 55, No. 2, pp. 609-615, February 2008.
- 17) Jurczak, M., Collaert, N., Veloso, A., Hoffmann, T., & Biesemans, S. (2009). Review of FINFET technology. In 2009 IEEE international SOI conference, pp. 1–4. IEEE
- 18) Dadoria, A. K., Khare, K., Gupta, T. K., & Singh, R. P. (2017). Leakage reduction by using FinFET technique for nanoscale technology circuits. *Journal of Nanoelectronics and Optoelectronics*, 12(3), 278–285
- 19) Guo, D., Karve, G., Tsutsui, G., Lim, K. Y., Robison, R., Hook, T., Vega, R., et al. (2016). FINFET technology featuring high mobility SiGe channel for 10nm and beyond. In 2016 IEEE Symposium on VLSI Technology, IEEE, 1–2
- 20) Yakimets, D., Bardon, M. G., Jang, D., Schuddinck, P., Sherazi, Y., Weckx, P., Miyaguchi, K., et al. (2017). Power aware FinFET and lateral nanosheet FET targeting for 3nm CMOS technology. 2017 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM) (pp. 20–24). IEEE
- 21) Garg, M., & Singh, B. (2017). A comparative performance analysis of cmos and finfet based voltage mode sense amplifier. In 2016 8th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks (CICN), IEEE, 544–547
- 22) T. Venkata Lakshmi, M. Kamaraju” A Review on SRAM Memory Design Using FinFET Technology”, *International Journal of System Dynamics Applications*, Volume 11, Issue 6, 2021
- 23) Rajprabu, R., Raj, A., V., and, & Rajnarayanan, R. (2013). Performance Analysis of CMOS and FinFET Logic. *IOSR Journal of VLSI and Signal Processing (IOSR-JVSP)*, 2(1), 1–6
- 24) Qiang Zhao, Chunyu Peng, Junning Chen, Zhiting Lin, and Xiulong Wu, “Novel Write-Enhanced and Highly Reliable RHPD-12T SRAM Cells for Space Applications”, *IEEE Transactions On Very Large Scale Integration (Vlsi) Systems*, 2020.
- 25) Suraj Singh Dohar, Siddharth R. K., Vasantha M.H., Nithin Kumar Y.B., “A Novel Single Event Upset Tolerant 12T Memory Cell for Aerospace Applications”, 2159-3477/20/, 2020, IEEE.

- 26) Young Bok Kim, "Design methodology based on carbon nanotube field effect transistor (CNFET)", Computer Engineering Dissertations, 2011.
- 27) Sang Hoon Chae, Young Hee Lee, "Carbon NanoTubes and graphene towards soft electronics," Nano Convergence 2014, pp.1-15.
- 28) Narendra Hanchate & N. Ranganathan, (2004), 'A New Technique for Leakage Reduction in CMOS Circuits using Self-Controlled Stacked Transistors', Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on VLSI Design (VLSID'04) IEEE.
- 29) Z. Chen, Y.-M. Lin, M. J. Rooks, and Ph. Avouris, "Graphene nano-ribbon electronics," *Physica E: Low-dimensional Syst. Nanostruct.*, vol. 40, pp. 228–232, 2007.
- 30) M. Y. Han, B. O' zylmaz, Y. Zhang, and P. Kim, "Energy band-gap engineering of graphene nanoribbons," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, vol. 98, pp. 206805- 1–206805-4, 2007.
- 31) X. Li, X. Wang, L. Zhang, S. Lee, and H. Dai, "Chemically derived, ultra smooth graphene nanoribbon semiconductors," *Science*, vol. 319, pp. 1229–1232, 2008.
- 32) Y.-W. Son, M. L. Cohen, and S. G. Louie, "Energy gaps in grapheme nanoribbons," *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, vol. 97, pp. 216803-1–216803-4, 2006.
- 33) K. S. Novoselov et al., "Electric field effect in atomically thin carbon films," *Science*, vol. 306, pp. 666–669, 2004.
- 34) Y. Zhang et al., "Experimental observation of the quantum Hall effect and Berry's phase in graphene," *Nature*, vol. 438, pp. 201–204, 2005.
- 35) C. Berger et al., "Electronic confinement and coherence in patterned epitaxial graphene," *Science*, vol. 312, pp. 1191–1196, 2006.
- 36) R. V. Noorden, "Moving towards a graphene world," *Nature*, vol. 442, pp. 228– 229, 2006.
- 37) X. Li et al., "Chemically derived, ultrasmooth graphene nanoribbon semiconductors," *Science*, vol. 319, pp. 1229–1232, 2008.
- 38) Niraj K. Jha, Deming Chen, "Nanoelectronic Circuit Design", Springer, 2011.
- 39) C. R. Manoj, Meenakshi Nagpal, Dhanya Varghese, and V. Ramgopal Rao, " Device Design and Optimization Considerations for Bulk FinFETs", *IEEE transactions on electron devices*, Vol. 55, No. 2, pp. 609-615, February 2008.
- 40) Joerg Appenzeller, "Carbon nanotubes for high performance electronics - Progress and prospect", *Purdue e-Pubs*, 2008.
- 41) R. Martel, T. Schmidt, H. R. Shea, T. Hertel, and Ph. Avouris, " Single- and multi-wall carbon nanotube field effect transistors", *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 73, no. 17, pp. 2447-2449, Oct. 1998.